

TOTAL QUALITY MANAGEMENT PRINCIPLES APPLIED WITHIN THE FIELD OF ROAD FREIGHT TRANSPORT: A SPECIFIC APPROACH

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Abstract

Purpose – Applying the principles of total quality management within organizations that operate in the road freight transport industry, additionally showcasing the potential effects of this strategic approach on an organization.

Methodology/approach – A medium sized road freight transport company operating in Romania was studied.

Findings – Total quality management fundamental principles can be applied within the specified field, with favorable consequences in terms of overall organizational performance.

Research limitations/implications – The research has been carried out upon studying the practices of a medium organization operating in the field of study. Thus, it is not possible to extrapolate the results unless further research is conducted.

Practical implications – Provide a clear understanding of how the fundamental principles of total quality management apply within the specific field and serve as a starting point for organizations in implementing a management system based on total quality.

Originality/value – This article presents itself as a starting point in studying total quality transportation applications within small and medium organisations operating in the road freight transport field. In addition, the study addresses the lack of research regarding the Romanian road transport industry.

Key words: road freight transport, total quality principles, competitive advantage.

Introduction

In the rapidly changing environment of the present era, the transportation sector plays an essential function in facilitating globalization. Road transport of goods and other commodities is the most utilized type of transport globally, given its inherent advantages (Bektaş, 2017). Transportation is essential in the supply chain and global economy since it facilitates the transfer of commodities from their origin to their destination. Thus, this activity enhances the value of the products and provides flexibility in their distribution (Lietuvnikė et al., 2017). Due to extended infrastructure, vehicles are able to reach destinations that cannot be served by any other method of transportation.

In today's economy, small and medium enterprises are crucial (Woźniak et al., 2019), being the key element that links microeconomics and macroeconomics (Distanont and Khongmalai, 2018). Therefore, understanding how these organizations function and proposing methods of improvement is of utmost importance in supporting overall economic development. It has been acknowledged that total quality management is a central pillar for enhancing company performance (Oakland, 1989; Žeželj, 2013; Yu et al., 2020).

This paper analyzes the adaptation of total quality management principles within an organization operating in the sector of road carriage of wholesale goods or other commodities. To accomplish its scope, a medium sized organization is the focus of the research. To support the importance of implementing this strategy, this piece of work will highlight the benefits of implementing total quality management in such organizations.

Literature review

Road freight transport

Road freight transport represents an essential activity in supporting the development and growth of the global economy (Garcia et al., 2008; Nowakowska-Grunt and Strzelczyk, 2019; Collaço et al., 2022). Without road freight, most of the activities carried out on a daily basis would come to a standstill and the supply chain would be destroyed. Thus, the road transport of goods is much more than a convoy of high-tonnage vehicles on the roads. Many academics and practitioners argue that the most used form of transport at a global scale is represented by road freight transport (Carboni et al., 2024; Nkesah, 2023; Stenico de Campos et al., 2019). Engström (2016) describes this mode of transport as "the blood" of modern society. This aspect is due to the advantageous characteristics of road freight transport, such as flexibility, adaptability and low costs.

The transport industry stands at the core of the functionality for modern human settlements and is crucial to connecting different markets globally. For any industry to function efficiently, road transport services are required. Thus, it is obvious that road freight transport organizations have a particularly important role in the global economy (McKinnon, 2019). Due to the significant and rapid growth of this industry, the competition is increasingly fierce. Thus, to maintain their market share and generate positive financial outcomes, organizations must also adapt operations to effectively compete with rivals, while simultaneously finding ways to cover the ongoing rise in expenses (Poliak et al., 2021).

On the other hand, road freight transport also gives rise to negative consequences, such as increasing the final cost of goods, polluting air and water, using scarce resources and favoring the occurrence of traffic accidents (Demir et al., 2014; Litman and Burwell, 2009; Nkesah, 2023). From this point of view, the activity of road transport of goods, although essential to contemporary society, can be identified as a very significant factor that partake in increased environmental degradation and, subsequently, worsen living conditions.

Competitive advantage

Competitive advantage represents an organization's capacity to outperform its competitors in terms of performance, through using techniques that differentiate the enterprise from its competitors such as lower pricing, superior quality of the services and increased customer satisfaction (Porter, 1998). In addition, this not only enables the business to enhance its profitability, but it also creates value for both the organization and its stakeholders (Kuncoro and Suriani, 2018). Furthermore, competitive advantage can be defined as a crucial element that sets an

organization's products or services apart from all other options available to customers from rival companies.

Competitive advantage can be established using diverse strategies (Christensen, 2001). It can emerge from executing certain aspects of the supply chain more effectively than rival companies (Li et al., 2006). Additionally, it can originate from distinctive resources and capabilities that are exclusive to the company (Bel, 2018). Moreover, assets, traits, and abilities that are difficult to duplicate or surpass by competitors establish a sustained competitive advantage, resulting in a stronger long-term market position. Furthermore, the benefit remains enduring only if competitors are unable to swiftly duplicate the exceptional product or service attributes. Therefore, the organization must possess a particular capacity that sets it apart from its competitors to create meaningful competitive advantage (Coyne, 1986). Ghemawat (1986) proposes that there are three primary categories of durable advantage: dominance in market share, superior access to resources or customers, and limitations on the competitor's alternatives. Moreover, Ghemawat (1986) asserts that none of these categories are mutually exclusive and that the greater their interaction, the more beneficial it is for the organization.

Porter's (1985) generic tactics claim that competitive advantage can stem from either differentiation or cost. Although his perspective may be accurate, his approach can only result in a temporary competitive edge. To attain enduring competitive advantage, a company should choose the Resource-Based View, supporting a framework in which both advantages can harmoniously coexist. Combining this technique with the stakeholder theory has proven to be a great strategy in obtaining competitive advantage (Freeman et. Al, 2021). Hence, positioning tactics offer only a transient advantage, while capability strategies offer a more enduring benefit (Huang et al., 2015).

Total Quality Management

According to theorists Chase and Aquilano (1992), total quality management may be defined as an extensive management method aimed at achieving excellence in all aspects of an organization's products and services, which are considered significant by the customer. This definition is limiting, as it focuses on quality perceived by the customer, and does not consider quality from the point of view of processes.

Oakland (1989) advocates total quality management as a strategic methodology that aims to enhance overall business efficiency and adaptability. The need for organizational alignment is noted in terms of systematic structuring and involvement of all components of an organization, including departments, activities and individuals at all hierarchical levels. However, Oakland's (1989) definition emphasizes quality from an organizational point of view, specifically process efficiency and finished product quality, but completely ignores quality from an external point of view.

Yu et al. (2020) define total quality management as the utilization of both qualitative techniques and human resources to enhance all organizational operations and surpass the present and future requirements of clients. Total quality management is described as a continuous organizational process in which executives take the necessary measures to provide an opportunity for everyone in the organization to set and achieve standards that are not only in alignment with the internal and external customers' needs and expectations, but they also overcome them (Miller, 1996).

Dihardjo and Ellitan (2021) argue that the implementation a total quality management system must be basen on solid principles. The three fundamental principles of total quality management represent: (1) focusing on the customer, (2) constant process enhancement and

(3) total involvement. Even if there are more principles of total quality management debated in literature and practice, this paper will focus solely on the fundamental ones.

Methodology

To accomplish the purpose of this study, a Romanian medium-sized company that operates in the selected industry has been chosen as the object of this study. Thus, its operations and daily activities were analyzed. First and foremost, the theoretical framework has been created to showcase concepts complementary to the field of road freight transport and total quality management. In addition, the three fundamental principles of this strategic approach were highlighted.

The company and its operations were observed over a period of 6 months. The next step of the research is to analyze all the activities carried out in a freight transport organization and identify areas of improvement. Moving on, the fundamental principles of total quality management have been applied and discussed, in order to showcase the benefits of this strategy.

Results

Customer focus

According to the findings of Tenner and Detoro (1992), the concept of customer focus involves understanding that the concept of quality is predicated on the premise that every individual in an organization has a customer and it is imperative to consistently meet their requirements, needs and expectations so that the organization as a whole can effectively respond to the external (final) customer's requirements. In a transport organization, it is of utmost importance that all departments work together in order to achieve quality. The information must flow accurately from one level to another, so that the final customer is satisfied with all the operations, which include the proper transport of the goods, timely information regarding any issues that may cause delays, precise delivery time and correct invoicing

A framework consisting of 3 main activities is defined through which organizations can more easily understand who their consumers are, what their needs are and how they can be met (Tenner and Detoro, 1992). First of all, it is necessary to identify the consumer, his needs and how they can be satisfied. Secondly, so that the requirements of clients are met and exceeded, identifying the product/service characteristics that the customer requests, the standard of performance of the product so that it can satisfy the needs, as well as the importance of the characteristics of the good or service and the alignment between consumer satisfaction and product performance represent aspects of utmost importance. Thirdly, the voice of the consumer needs to be heard, and this can be achieved from both the supplier and consumer perspectives. Within a road freight organization, the application of this principle is fundamental, as customer requests are specific and the service must be customized in relation to them. Figure 1 showcases the application of this principle in a transport organization and how it is strongly linked to the second principle of total quality management.

Figure 1. Customer focused approach in road freight transport

Constant process improvement

The second quality principle refers to continuous process improvement, which aims to use precise methodologies and metrics to systematically collect and evaluate data in order to improve processes considered vital to the organization's mission (Jurov and Barnard, 1993). The continuous improvement of processes, especially through the use of a PDCA-type strategy, is an essential activity within a transport organization, as it allows the early identification of possible problems and facilitates their solution, without causing other repercussions. Overall customer satisfaction can also be increased through this process. The use of evidence-based information and feedback channels is also essential for continuous process improvement. Data analysis, performance indicators and customer feedback can help freight companies identify weaknesses or consumer dissatisfaction.

Every freight transport company aspiring to increase efficiency, lower costs and enhance servicing activities uses continuous process improvement. This approach encourages continuous review, modification and improvement in all operations so that the service provided can meet and even exceed customer expectations and needs (Shortell et al., 1998). Thus, customer satisfaction can be directly linked to process improvement, as shown in Figure 2. Continuous process improvement involves systematically examining workflows, methods and systems to pinpoint areas that need enhancement. In a road freight company, this may involve reviewing loading protocols, optimizing routes and scheduling deliveries. More precisely, transport planning should be done as soon as possible after receiving a transport order, and the expected delivery time should be as accurate as possible. By regularly reviewing these

operational factors, organizations can identify inefficiencies, blockages and opportunities for optimization.

Figure 2. The relationship between process improvement and customer satisfaction

A culture of continuous process improvement requires company-wide participation and cooperation (Tan and Wisner, 2001). Employees should be empowered to make proposals, present new ideas and actively solve problems. Suggestion programs, cross-functional teams, and frequent performance reviews can help firms encourage ownership and responsibility for change. Also, in order to be able to ensure the effectiveness of strategies for constant quality improvement, it is necessary for people in management to adopt this attitude and support change initiatives.

Total involvement

The last fundamental principle to be discussed is the total involvement of all departments and hierarchical levels within an organization. Thus, all employees, regardless of their hierarchical position, are given the power to collaboratively improve their work environment (Dihardjo and Ellitan, 2021). This is achieved through a flexible organizational framework that enables them to collectively address issues, improve operational procedures and effectively meet customer expectations. Within a road freight organization, this process can only be accomplished

through increased communication within the organization and effective centralization of information. Given the interdependence of processes and operations within a transportation organization, it is necessary for administrative staff to be alert not only to issues flagged by data analysis, but also to those noted by personnel performing transportation operations.

In relevant literature, total quality management in transport is called total quality transport. The use of the term total quality transportation (TQT) is used as an alternative to total quality management to redirect the focus away from the preconceived assumptions associated with total quality management and to emphasize the commitment to providing high quality transportation services, encouraging developing existing skills, learning and promoting a sense of pride among employees in their efforts to provide exceptional service (Metri, 2006). Total quality transportation users adhere to a transportation service philosophy centered on customer orientation and continuous improvement. This philosophy encompasses several key elements, including a commitment to meet or exceed customer requirements, active involvement of a significant number of stakeholders, use of statistical tools for analysis, continuous evaluation of processes, demonstration of strong quality leadership, delivery of training and retraining, improving safety measures, analyzing current performance, implementing a green transport system and complying with local needs and regulations.

For an organization to achieve optimal efficiency, it is imperative that all components within the organization function cohesively, recognizing the interconnectedness of individuals and activities. In addition, total quality management is a systematic approach aimed at eliminating individual inefficiencies by including all stakeholders in improvement processes. Its main objective is to increase work efficiency to achieve the desired results in short time intervals.

Discussion and conclusions

Given the fact that this market allows for slight to no service differentiation, companies should focus on other resources that can be used in order to create, sustain and enhance competitive advantage. Thus, total quality management should be one of the key organizational processes, as it enables the establishment of a durable competitive advantage and differentiation from the competition. Total quality management is applied in all departments within a road freight transport organization, such as, but not limited to: logistics, accounting, human resources or operational departments. The principles and strategies related to total quality management are to be applied at the level of the entire organization, including all its functions.

Constant process improvement is cyclical, focusin on increasing quality from an organizational point of view, and on increasing the quality perceived by the customer. Total quality management within a road freight organization is concerned with cost efficiency, by optimizing transport routes and fuel consumption rationing, shortening working times in terms of internal processes (e.g. introduction, operation and data analysis, as well as their transmission, can be made more efficient by using specialized software).

The implications of this paper are limited due to the specific research method. Taking into account that only one company has been studied, the results cannot be used as a benchmark for generalisation. Thus, further exploration on the topic is needed in order to extrapolate. However, the outcomes of this study may serve as a treshold in understanding how the principles of total quality management apply within an organisation that provides road freight transport services.

References

Bel, R.

2018.

"A property rights theory of competitive advantage". *Strategic Management Journal*, 39:1678-1703.

Bektaş, T.

2017

"Freight Transport and Distribution: Concepts and Optimization Models" (1st ed.). CRC Press. <https://doi.org/10.1201/9781315173962>

Carboni, M., Dall-Orsoletta, A., Hawkes, A. and Giarola, S.

2024

"The future of road freight transport and alternative technologies: A case study for Italy." *Energy Conversion and Management*, 299:117819. Science Direct. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enconman.2023.117819>

Chase, R.B. and Aquilano, N.J.

1991

"Production and Operations Management" (6th ed), Homewood: Irwin

Christensen, C.M.

2001

"The Past and Future of Competitive Advantage." *MIT Sloan Management Review*, 42(2):105. <https://teaching.up.edu/BUS580/bps/Christensen,%202001,%20Past%20and%20future%20of%20comp%20advantage.pdf>

Collaço, F. M. de A., Teixeira, A. C. R., Machado, P. G., Borges, R. R., Brito, T. L. F. and Mouette, D.

2022

"Road Freight Transport Literature and the Achievements of the Sustainable Development Goals — A Systematic Review." *Sustainability*, 14(6):3425. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su14063425>

Coyne, K.P.

1986

"What it is, what it isn't." *Business Horizons*, 29(1):54-61. <https://reader.elsevier.com/reader/sd/pii/000768138690087X?token=4982D459BA8B75EB94DF7504D96EB140A80E7D1415CC6B7939DDDA190B21B657457B0FCEF2ABBC82D0720CC808180E58>

Demir, E., Bektaş, T., and Laporte, G.

2014

"A review of recent research on green road freight transportation." *European Journal of Operational Research*, 237(3):775–793. Science Direct. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ejor.2013.12.033>

Dihardjo, D. and Ellitan, L.

2021

"Total Quality Management: A Review of Recent Trend." *International Journal of Trend in Research and Development*, 8(6):40–45. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/355955448_Total_Quality_Management_A_Review_of_Recent_Trend

Distanont and Khongmalai

2018

"The role of innovation in creating competitive advantage." *Kasetsart Journal of Social Sciences*, 41:15-21

Engström, R.

2016

"The Roads' Role in the Freight Transport System." *Transportation Research Procedia*, 14:1443–1452. Elsevier. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.trpro.2016.05.217>

Freeman, R.E, Dmytriiev, S.D. and Phillips, R.A.

2020

"Stakeholder Theory and the Resource-Based View of the Firm". *Journal of Management*, 47(7):1757-1770. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0149206321993576>

Garcia, C., Levy, S., Limão, S., and Kupfer, F.

2008

"Correlation between Transport Intensity and GDP in European Regions: a New Approach." Paper presented at the 8th Swiss Transport Research Conference, Monte Verità, Switzerland. https://www.strc.ch/2008/2008_Garcia_Levy_Limao_Kupfer_TransportIntensity_GDP.pdf

Ghemawat, P.

1986

"Sustainable Advantage." *Harvard Business Review*. <https://hbr.org/1986/09/sustainable-advantage>

Huang, K.F., Dyerson, R., Wu, L.Y and Harindranath, G.

2015

"From Temporary Competitive Advantage to Sustainable Competitive Advantage" *British Journal of Management*, 26(4):617-636

Jurow, S., and Barnard, S. B.

1993

"Introduction: TQM Fundamentals and Overview of Contents." *Journal of Library Administration*, 18(1-2):1–13. https://doi.org/10.1300/j111v18n01_01

Kuncoro, W. and Suriani, W. O.

2018

"Achieving sustainable competitive advantage through product innovation and market driving." *Asia Pacific Management Review*, 23(3):186-192. Science Direct. <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S1029313215200966>

Litman, T. and Burwell, D.

2006

"Issues in sustainable transportation." *International Journal of Global Environmental Issues*, 6(4):331. <https://doi.org/10.1504/ijgenvi.2006.010889>

Li, S., Ragu-Nathan, B., Ragu-Nathan, T.S., Subba Rao, S.

2006

"The impact of supply chain management practices on competitive advantage and organizational performance" *Omega*, 34(2):107-124. Science Direct. <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/abs/pii/S0305048304001343>

Lietuvnikė, M.M., Zinkevičiūtė, V. and Vasilis Vasiliauskas, A.

2017

"Core problems the road freight transport companies face due to the refugee crisis." *Innovative Infotechnologies for Science, Business and Education*, 2(23):3–9. <https://etalpykla.vilniustech.lt/handle/123456789/118454>

McKinnon, A.

2019

"Freight transport and logistics." In Stanley, J and Hensher, D. A., "A Research Agenda for Transport Policy, 99-107, Cheltenham: Edward Elgar Publishing Limited

Miller, W. J.

1996

"A working definition for total quality management (TQM) researchers." *Journal of Quality Management*, 1(2):149–159. ScienceDirect. [https://doi.org/10.1016/s1084-8568\(96\)90011-5](https://doi.org/10.1016/s1084-8568(96)90011-5)

Nkesah, S. K.

2023

"Making road freight transport more Sustainable: Insights from a systematic literature review." *Transportation Research Interdisciplinary Perspectives*, 22. Science Direct. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.trip.2023.100967>

Nowakowska-Grunt, J. and Strzelczyk, M.

2019

"The current situation and the directions of changes in road freight transport in the European Union." *Transportation Research Procedia*, 39:350–359. Science Direct. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.trpro.2019.06.037>

Oakland, J.S.

1989

"Total quality management: the route to improving performance." Butterworth-Heinemann: Oxford

Poliak, M., Poliakova, A., Svabova, L., Zhuravleva, N. A. and Nica, E.

2021

"Competitiveness of Price in International Road Freight Transport." *Journal of Competitiveness*, 13(2):83–98. <https://doi.org/10.7441/joc.2021.02.05>

Porter, M.E.

1985

"The Competitive Advantage: Creating and Sustaining Superior Performance" New York: Free Press

Porter, M.E.

1998

"Competitive Strategy: Techniques for analyzing industries and competitors" New York:Free Press

Shortell, S. M., Bennett, C. L., and Byck, G. R.

1998

"Assessing the Impact of Continuous Quality Improvement on Clinical Practice: What It Will Take to Accelerate Progress." The Milbank Quarterly, 76(4):593–624. Wiley. <https://doi.org/10.1111/1468-0009.00107>

Stenico de Campos, R., Tadeu Simon, A. and de Campos Martins, F.

2019

"Assessing the impacts of road freight transport on sustainability: A case study in the sugar-energy sector." Journal of Cleaner Production, 220:995–1004. Science Direct. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2019.02.171>

Tan, K. C., and Wisner, J. D.

2001

"A Framework for Quality Improvement in the Transportation Industry." Quality Management Journal, 8(1):9–22. Taylor and Francis. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10686967.2001.11918934>

Tenner, A.R. and Detoro, I.J.

1992

"Total quality management: three steps to continuous improvement." Addison-Wesley>

Woźniak, M., Duda, J., Gąsior, A. and Bernat, T.

2019

"Relations of GDP growth and development of SMEs in Poland" Procedia Computer Science, 159:2470-2480. Science Direct. <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S1877050919316278>

Yu, G.J., Park, M., and Hong, K.H.

2020

"A strategy perspective on total quality management." Total Quality Management and Business Excellence, 31(1-2):68-81

Žeželj, S.

2013

"The Implementation of a Quality Management System> A Case Study of Serbian Transport Organizations." International Journal for Traffic and Transport Engineering, 3(4):397-407. [http://ijtte.com/uploads/2013-12-30/5ebd908d-79d1-31e3IJTTE_Vol%203\(4\)_4.pdf](http://ijtte.com/uploads/2013-12-30/5ebd908d-79d1-31e3IJTTE_Vol%203(4)_4.pdf)